

A Nationalist Approach towards Science and Technology: A Review of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Roy's *Collected Essays* in Bengali

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When a disrupted, wounded civilisation, repeatedly colonised by external forces of aggression, made to suffer the ignominy of losing all contacts with its glorious past the registers and records of which were brutally destroyed, finally woke up to the necessity of *revival*, it gave birth to Acharya Prafulla Chandra Roy. The Hindu revival of nineteenth century India is not just an attempt to restore the present to a vantage position where the glories of the ancients are rediscovered, but an impossible struggle to match them in terms of scholarly, creative, scientific innovations. That quest for the rediscovery of India and the endeavour to move forward in a spirit of free thinking are evident in every word of this Bengali

collection of articles and essays of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Roy titled *Prabandhasamgraha* (Probondhoshongroho).

The general Bengali indifference to science and technology is conjoined with the Bengali apathy to industry (both in the ancient sense of hard work and the modern sense of factories of mass production). Such indifference and apathy provide a stark study in contrast, if investigated vis-a-vis the general Bengali celebration of culture; it is no coincidence that Tagore's university Visva Bharati attached no importance to commerce, science and technology while insisting on humanities and fine arts. It is therefore commensurate that Acharya Prafulla Chandra Roy's response to the Bengali lacunae offers a synthesis of science and technology with commerce. That the Bengali *bhadraloks* have repeatedly failed to assign due significance to science, technology and commerce is intimately associated with their comprador status, as the present writer would like to maintain (a hypothesis that was originally offered in the very inaugural issue of JBS).

A certain divorce between arts and the material spheres of activity that included commerce, science and technology was necessitated by the historical dynamics of the reigning comprador class which needed to forget the sheer material weight of colonial reality, and instead celebrated its literary and intellectual excellence in a desperate attempt to compensate for its disempowered status. It was none other than Acharya Prafulla Chandra (henceforth APC) who was bestowed with knighthood and offered Fellowship of Royal Society for his works on science who recognised that the Bengali obsession with university degrees is a characteristic crisis of a morally, economically subservient people.

But significantly, an emphasis on financial activity and scientific quest earmark the early developments within the Bengal Renaissance, which are lost later in the twentieth century, as APC notes, and hails Akshaykumar Dutta for his articles on physics published in *Tottobodhini Potrika*, Rajendralal

for his works on geology and natural science in Bibidhartho Shongroho, Krishnamohan for his *Encyclopedia Bengalensis* (356-357). Why the independent pursuit of scientific knowledge and Bengali entrepreneurship deteriorated throughout nineteenth century and reached an abysmal rock bottom in the twentieth century (despite golden opportunities offered by freedom struggle which involved a boycott of Government run educational institutions and British products) may perhaps be answered by a recourse to the system of *Permanent Settlement* introduced by Lord Cornwallis in Bengal in 1793. This is the opinion of APC: that the Bengali elites by the end of eighteenth century accept the status of zamindar as almost the final attainment of nirvana (77). It goes without saying that the middle classes responded by inventing their own form of permanent settlement which was trying to become salaried or skilled professionals with university degrees: clerks, doctors, engineers, lawyers. As a result, any quest for innovation suffered fundamentally, jeopardising the ability to independently and creatively engage with science and commerce. A static inertia came to reign. However, there were exceptions which APC does not always seem to notice. In spite of being a salaried officer of the British Government, Bankim Chandra Chatterjee himself wrote at length on science. Sukumar Roy and his father Upendrakishore are examples of that seamless alignment between culture and commerce, between printing technology and literary art.

Terry Eagleton in his *Ideology of the Aesthetic* speaks of that definite moment of the advent of European modernity which separated the cognitive from the aesthetic and the ethical: but it is significant to note that in the ancient Indian flourish of science and technology (the chronicles of which APC records in his *History of Hindu Chemistry*) no such fragmentation and dissociation take place. APC himself refers to the 64 *Kalas* (literally the 64 arts) which conjoined the aesthetic and the cognitive: all disciplines from sexual ethics to metallurgy came under the *Kalas*. APC notes that the 64 *Kalas* included *ratnapariksha* which was the science of precious stones, *dhaatuvada*, which was metallurgy, and the study of alkali, among other sciences (228). Needless to say they included poetry, instrumental music, dancing, and

singing as well.

APC himself mixes the different spheres with an admirable alacrity. He chairs and addresses a Bengali literary conference, and traces the evolution of Bengali prose in his address that may outshine the oeuvres of any professional literary historian. He chairs the provincial congress of Hindu Mahasabha and offers a clear, straightforward picture of the imminent crisis of the Hindus of Bengal in a manner worthy of a scientist (in this regard he cites a statistical survey done by Dr Upendra Nath Mukherjee which exhibits the dangerous decline of Hindu population in Bengal; it is a pity that the said treatise of U N Mukherjee, titled “The Dying Race” is now out of print, and no longer easily available in any library either. In recent times, renowned environmentalist (and also a social scientist and a social critic) Mohit Ray has worked on this similar issue and has come up with similar conclusions: Bengali speaking Hindus indeed seem to be a dying race. There is no doubt that APC was a clear-sighted, far-sighted nationalist. APC spoke of the ancient Hindu glory of the indigenous achievements in science and technology in his seminal work *A History of Hindu Chemistry*, but he was more concerned about the present as well as future of the Bengalis.

In suggesting the remedy of scientific and commercial quest to the dying race of the Bengalis, APC is often overtly enchanted with the Victorian doctrines of individualism, the fairy tales of capitalist modernity which describe the journey of the protagonist from rags to riches, the fascination with the Samuel Smile type self-help doctrines, the stories of individual genius, he cannot perhaps entirely be faulted. All around him classical capitalism was triumphant, and Bengalis failed to learn a lesson from that. A nationalist and indigenous bourgeois class was absent to the detriment of Bengal, which, as APC rightly noted, would eventually bring the decimation of the Bengali people. But it is imperative to note that APC does not sufficiently emphasise on collective efforts, at times, and seems to be too much enamoured with individualism, a typical philosophy of late nineteenth and early twentieth century. But

he is able to note the potential in Hindu castes for collectively furthering technology and commerce, which is evident from his address to the Konshobonik (caste of bronze merchants) conference.

APC is considered as a champion of the Bengali people, and rightly so. If there was any Bengali nationalist in British India, it was him. It is amazing to note that his holistic approach to science and technology is matched by his attempt to locate the Bengalis firmly within the shared Hindu context. In other words, he traces an unbroken civilisational chain that connects the Bengalis with their neighbours, and connects the Bengali present to a shared Indian past. *A History of Hindu Chemistry* is an illustration of the latter, while his active and enthusiastic chronicling of Assamese literature remarkably establishes how he wants to see the Bengalis within the eastern Indian civilisation. APC laments the fact that the commercial ventures of Kolkata are not in the hands of the Bengalis themselves, and says without caring for political correctness: “It is the Marwari conquest apart from the British conquest that has impoverished Bengal” (508-9). But it is interesting to note that APC wants intermarriage to take place among the Bengalis and Marwaris, so that a hybrid people emerge with the best characteristics of both. He may be too much enamoured with a Shavian eugenics.

Coming back to that modern dissociation of cognition and aesthetics, or art and science, it is interesting to note that any nationalist movement will always try to bridge this gap that may exist between its technological and cultural dimensions. Nationalism is a catholic movement that offers a synthesis of different human spheres in a characteristic gesture of post-enlightenment radicalism, and Eagleton himself tries to draw a trajectory of the alliance of science and culture in the nationalist movement of Ireland in *Scholars and Rebels*. We may argue that nationalism is a characteristically post-enlightenment movement, and that it attempts to overcome the separation and reification of various human spheres of activity (structurally akin to the rise of atomic, antagonistic individuals alienated from each other who can come together only by virtue of some social contract). It is a matter of great curiosity that ancient

India which had its enlightenment (Buddha means the enlightened one, but apart from that literal meaning, we may note that a highly materialistic, highly organic civilisation flourished in ancient India), did not find any difficulty in reconciling its spiritual basis with its material activities.

Moreover, the question of physical labour was never dissociated from intellectual pursuit in India, which seems to have been the case of ancient Greco-Roman civilisation. The anecdote of Charak/Sushruta roaming in a forest in search of a non-medicinal herb indicates that the doctor/chemist did his works first hand, and did not depend on servile labour. In any case, slavery was not a social practice in India the way it was in Greece and Rome. Further, the question of practical experiment was emphasised in ancient Hindu texts of chemistry to the point that anyone whoever was not capable of practically demonstrating the processes described in theoretical chemistry was called an actor instead of a teacher or a pupil, as APC points out (214).

APC repeatedly speaks of the juncture between science and art: he is a patriot scientist, and he challenges the liberal notion of disinterested pursuit. APC is unabashedly inclined towards his own people, the Bengali people, and he celebrates the spirit of freedom struggle in technology that aids in commerce and industries, and ultimately paves the way for a national self-reliance of the Bengali people. No one in modern times has probably emphasised on the role of industry and business among the de-industrialised and ill-intellectualised lot of the twentieth century Bengalis the way APC has done.

APC was not just a scientist. He was a great teacher, as we can see in the fond recollection of his student Dilip Kumar Roy (son of D L Roy; a great singer, writer and a yogi associated with Sri Aurobindo). Deeply patriotic and an upholder of the ancient Hindu glory, APC was an instrumental force of social reformation as well, and fought against all the stagnant, retrograde shackles of superstitions which retarded the growth of independent query that lies at the heart of the endeavours of science. The second volume of Dilip Kumar Roy's *Rochonashongroho* records an episode from the classroom of APC

that leaves no one in any doubt that here was a teacher whose great love for the Hindu legacy of science and technology was matched by his merciless criticism of the backward, unthinking conformity of the present day Hindus to the shibboleths of mindless superstitions (57).

APC's writings are a small part of his relentless activism towards a scientific, rational, objective outlook which he wanted to promote among the Bengalis and in this sense, he is a forerunner of the popular science and rationalism movement in Bengal, which later came to be hijacked by communists of various hues, culminating in a complete dissociation of organic sensibility and cultural legacy from the scientific-rational spirit, a process imaginatively depicted by writer Nabarun Bhattacharya in *Herbert* with admirable dexterity. In APC's science movement, an organic nationalism comes to champion the promotion of popular scientific thinking among the masses, as manifested in his advocacy of indigenous food habits, promotion of dairy farming, and above all, celebration of the marriage of technology and nationalist entrepreneurship, the epitome of which was his legendary venture named Bengal Chemical. The history of Bengal Chemical is educative. Its saga fills us with joy and sorrow, as APC himself continues to offer us severe admonishment and infinite inspiration even today.

Roy, Acharya Prafulla Chandra. *Prabandhasamgraha* (Collected Essays). Kolkata: Dey's Publishing, 2012.

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